

Curated Resource List: Using EdTech in Crisis-Affected Settings

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Reviewers Saalim Koomar and Kate Radford

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Terminology

AI	Artificial Intelligence
EiE	Education in Emergencies
EMIS	Education management information systems
FLN	Foundational literacy and numeracy
GenAI	Generative AI
ICT	Information and communications technology
LMIC	Low- and middle-income country
MEL	Monitoring, evaluation, and learning
RCT	Randomised controlled trial
SEL	Social and emotional learning
USSD	Unstructured Supplementary Service Data

Organisations

AHEEN	African Higher Education in Emergencies Network
ECW	Education Cannot Wait
DFID	Department of International Development
ECW	Education Cannot Wait
FCDO	Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (UK)
GPE	Global Partnership for Education
GGHEiE	Geneva Global Hub for Education in Emergencies
INEE	Inter-Agency Network for Education in Emergencies
IRC	International Rescue Committee
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
RTI	RTI International
STS	School-to-School International
UNGEI	United Nations Girls' Education Initiative
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Key definitions

Education in emergencies: We have adapted the definition provided by the [↑INEE \(2024\)](#) and define ‘education in emergencies’ as the quality of current and future learning opportunities for children of primary and secondary-level age in situations of crisis, including non-formal education.

Crisis-affected: We use Education Cannot Wait’s definition of ‘crisis-affected’, namely: “affected by armed conflict, forced displacement, climate-induced and geophysical hazards, epidemics, or socio-economic challenges [...] the term ‘crisis-affected’ reflects a broader educational vulnerability, capturing both disrupted access and diminished education quality in countries affected by crises” ([↑Education Cannot Wait, 2025](#), p. 7).

EdTech: We use the following definition of educational technology (EdTech): “Technologies—including hardware, software, and digital content—that are either designed or appropriated for educational purposes” ([↑Hennessy et al., 2021](#), p. 8).

Education types: Drawing from the [↑United Nations Girls’ Education Initiative \(UNGEI\) et al. \(2021\)](#), we adopt the following definitions:

- **Alternative education:** alternative education includes planned, structured education programming for out-of-school children, adolescents, and youth that leads to equivalent, certified competencies in academic or technical/vocational subjects. Alternative education is usually flexible to accommodate and meet the needs of out-of-school learners. Examples include:
 - Accelerated education programmes (AEPs): Flexible, age-appropriate programmes, run in a shorter timeframe, which aim to provide access to education for disadvantaged, over-age, out-of-school children and youth—particularly those who missed out on, or had their education interrupted due to poverty, marginalisation, conflict and crisis.
 - Alternative basic education.
 - Youth livelihoods training programmes.
- **Formal and non-formal education**
 - **Formal education** is education that is institutionalised, intentional and planned through public organisations and recognised private bodies and, in their totality, make up the formal education system of a country. Formal education

programmes are thus recognised as such by the relevant national educational authorities or equivalent, e.g., any other institution in co-operation with the national or sub-national educational authorities. Formal education consists mostly of initial education. Vocational education, special needs education and some parts of adult education are often recognised as being part of the formal education system.

- **Non-formal education (NFE)** is the overarching term that refers to planned, structured, and organised education programmes that are outside the formal education system. Some types of NFE lead to equivalent, certified competencies, while others do not. NFE programmes are characterised by their variety, flexibility, and ability to respond quickly to the new educational needs of learners in a given context, as well as by their holistic, learner-centred pedagogy. Informal learning (knowledge and skills naturally obtained through day-to-day interactions and activities) is not considered NFE.
- **Support Services:** Drawing from the [↑United Nations Girls' Education Initiative \(UNGEI\) et al. \(2021\)](#), we define support services as including programmes offered to students in addition to their formal or non-formal education studies. Examples include:
 - Tutoring and after-school support
 - Remedial education
 - Dropout prevention and learning readiness
 - Integrated curriculum elements, such as life skills, health education, disaster risk reduction, safety, psychosocial support and social-emotional learning, and peace education
 - Cash grants to facilitate enrolment and retention (e.g., for fees, uniforms, rewards for retention).
- **Transitional programmes:** Drawing from the [↑United Nations Girls' Education Initiative \(UNGEI\) et al. \(2021\)](#), we define transitional programmes as short-term educational programmes that help learners transition into formal or alternative education pathways. On their own, they do not lead to certification or equivalent competencies and are often implemented by non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Examples include:

- Learning readiness programmes
- Catch-up programmes
- Bridging programmes (e.g., language support)

Blended learning: We use an adapted version of [Graham's \(2006\)](#) definition of blended learning systems to refer to a combination of face-to-face instruction with technology-mediated instruction.

Hybrid learning: We adopt [INEE's \(2024\)](#) definition of 'hybrid learning' as an educational approach where some individuals participate in person and some participate online at the same time using technology.

Remote learning: We adopt [UNICEF & EdTech Hub's \(2022, p. vi\)](#) definition of remote learning: "[...] a method of learning where the teacher and learner are not physically present together in an academic institution for reasons related to accommodation and/or in response to emergency situations."

Delivery model: We define 'delivery model' as a description of how the instruction is delivered and timed. Instruction delivery is either face-to-face or technology-mediated, while the timing of instruction is either in real time (synchronous) or not in real time (asynchronous).

Technologies are the different channels through which EdTech can be delivered. Examples are radio broadcasts, television broadcasts, podcasts, text-messaging, educational games, online learning platforms, and e-readers. We have opted for the term 'technologies' as opposed to 'modalities' because 'modalities' is also used in some of the literature to describe delivery models.

1. Background

In 2020, EdTech Hub published [↑Using EdTech to Support Effective Data Monitoring: A Curated Resource List \(Koomar & Blest, 2020\)](#) in response to a helpdesk request from the World Bank Yemen team. The purpose of the publication was to explore how EdTech, and education interventions more widely, could be leveraged to support distance and alternative learning opportunities for people living in settings of fragility, conflict, and violence. It drew on peer-reviewed literature, policy guidance, and intervention documentation to identify practical, actionable EiE resources published after 2010 in medium- and high-intensity conflict settings. The publication focused particularly on EdTech interventions in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region and aimed to offer practical recommendations for tech-enabled EiE interventions in light of the Covid-19 pandemic

Since then, crises globally have continued to impact educational opportunities for the world's most vulnerable people. Today, an estimated 234 million children in crisis settings need education support, with 85 million out of school ([↑Education Cannot Wait, 2025](#)). Only 17% of primary-school-age children in these settings attend school and reach minimum reading proficiency ([↑Education Cannot Wait, 2025](#)). Children with disabilities, like other marginalised groups, are even more likely to have never attended school and to remain illiterate at age 15 ([↑GGHEIE, 2024](#)). When quality education is available, it strengthens children's resilience, supports their health and well-being, and improves their long-term economic prospects, as well as those of their communities and countries ([↑Education Cannot Wait, 2025](#); [↑The International Commission on Financing Global Education Opportunity, 2016](#)).

2. Document purpose and methodology

Since 2020, the use of EdTech in crisis-affected contexts has changed with the introduction of new technologies, the growth of some interventions, and the closure of others ([↑Barnes et al., 2025](#); [↑Brugha et al., 2025](#)).

Accordingly, this document updates [↑Using EdTech to Support Effective Data Monitoring: A Curated Resource List \(Koomar & Blest, 2020\)](#) to include both new interventions that have emerged since 2020 and new evidence on previously identified resources generated over the same period.

The updated list is based on a combination of systematic searching and screening using Google Scholar and the main Google search engine, alongside more pragmatic and targeted searches informed by the lead writers' experience. The search captures both peer-reviewed research and relevant grey literature from organisations working on EiE interventions in crisis-affected settings. It also draws on existing outputs developed by EdTech Hub, particularly those produced through the EiE and climate portfolio.

The inclusion criteria for this updated list is as follows:

- **Geographic scope:** MENA, Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), Eastern Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Asia.
- **Educational level:** Emphasis on primary and early secondary education, with select higher education interventions included.
- **Date range:** 2010–2026, with particular emphasis on 2020–2026. Earlier literature is included only where it remains important for understanding key EdTech interventions and where more recent evidence is limited.
- **Literature type:** Academic and grey literature. Because intervention evidence is often published in reports rather than journal articles, and recent findings may not yet appear in peer-reviewed publications, relevant grey literature is included. This literature is limited to material published or endorsed by a recognised government agency or non-governmental organisation operating in the crisis-affected sector.
- **Implementation and effectiveness:** Included sources provide details on how crisis-affected interventions have been implemented and, crucially, how effective that implementation has been. Evidence of effectiveness is drawn from a range of research designs and

methods, including self-report, A/B testing, randomised controlled trials, and others. Please note that, given the continually changing evidence landscape, this report provides only a snapshot of information and should be interpreted as a summary of the evidence base rather than an evaluation of methodological rigour.

- **Status of original interventions:** Interventions included in the original document are reassessed to determine whether additional evidence has emerged and whether they remain relevant or operational. The updated list reflects these changes.

In addition, this curated list focuses on crisis-affected settings rather than using terms such as ‘fragile settings’ or ‘settings of conflict, fragility and violence’. In updating the list of interventions, some interventions now have additional evidence, some are no longer operating or no longer appear relevant for inclusion, and others have been added that did not feature in the original report. In light of these changes, the thematic groupings used in the 2020 publication have also been revised. [Appendix A: Summary of interventions](#) shows a full overview of the interventions included in this review.

3. EdTech interventions in crisis-affected contexts

This section lists the various interventions located in crisis-affected settings and is divided into four subsections:

1. **Teaching and learning interventions.** Covers learner-facing interventions that directly support teaching, learning, skills development, and educational continuity in crisis-affected settings.
2. **Teacher professional development.** Includes interventions that strengthen teachers' pedagogical practice, digital capability, and capacity to support learning in crisis-affected settings.
3. **Access and enabling technologies.** Covers openly available platforms, learning content (i.e. global libraries), and enabling infrastructure that support equitable access to education and/or educational content in crisis-affected settings.
4. **System and policy.** This category includes interventions that support education planning, coordination, governance, and policy implementation in crisis-affected settings.

Each entry below includes a brief description of the intervention with recent evidence on results, the learning focus (i.e. FLN, multilingual), education type (i.e. formal vs nonformal), and the technology(s) employed.

3.1. Teaching and learning interventions

This subsection explores learner-facing interventions that directly support teaching, learning, skills development, and educational continuity in crisis-affected settings.

3.1.1. Ahlan Simsim

Ahlan Simsim is an early childhood development initiative for EiE settings launched in 2017 by Sesame Workshop and the International Rescue Committee ([↑Sesame Workshop, 2023](#)). Developed in response to the Syrian conflict, it supports children and families affected by displacement across the MENA. The initiative combines mass media, digital platforms, and direct services to strengthen early childhood development, early learning, and psychosocial support (PSS), with a particular focus on resilience, emotional regulation, and foundational cognitive skills in young children. It also addresses a major gap in humanitarian response, where

early childhood services are often overlooked ([↑Moustafa & Mtungwa, 2025](#); [↑Sesame Workshop, 2024](#)).

The initiative has reached more than 3.5 million children and caregivers through direct services, alongside far wider reach through its television programming ([↑Sesame Workshop, 2024](#)). A cluster randomised controlled trial in Jordan found gains in children's emotional knowledge and in expressive emotion regulation, though not across every measured outcome. A separate randomised controlled trial of the phone-based Reach Up and Learn model in Jordan found a small but statistically significant reduction in caregiver depressive symptoms, but no clear effects on anxiety or most parenting outcomes. In Lebanon, another randomised controlled trial found that the Remote Early Learning Programme produced significant improvements across all six child outcomes measured, including literacy, numeracy, motor development, play, and social-emotional skills. Taken together, these studies suggest that Ahlan Simsim has shown promising effects for child development, while evidence for caregiver outcomes is more mixed and depends on the intervention model being used ([↑Moustafa & Mtungwa, 2025](#)).

Learning focus: Early childhood development; psychosocial support

Education type: Non-formal education; support service

Technology: TV; digital platforms; mobile-based learning

3.1.2. Akelius Digital Learning Initiative

The Akelius Digital Learning Initiative was launched by UNICEF in 2018 and is active in 12 countries across both formal and non-formal education settings. The initiative provides a mobile application designed to support language learning for marginalised children, including refugee and displaced learners. While the application can be used autonomously by learners, UNICEF also provides technical and pedagogical support to education centres and teachers who integrate it into broader instruction. The app offers 11 free language courses featuring multimedia content organised into thematic chapters. Lessons include interactive activities such as vocabulary drills, grammar practice, quizzes, songs, and games. The application also incorporates gamified elements, allowing learners to earn virtual coins that can be exchanged for accessories for a digital avatar ([↑Barnes & Katrin, 2025](#); [↑UNICEF Innocenti, 2024](#)).

Internal evaluations of the Akelius digital learning application with displaced learners in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece, Italy, and Lebanon

were part of a broader implementation research effort that combined qualitative and quantitative methods, while using country-specific learning measures rather than one standardised tool across contexts. In Greece, the evaluation used propensity score matching with 949 students, while in Lebanon researchers used an empirical model controlling for individual characteristics, location fixed effects, and baseline learning levels, with a sample of 10,711 students. In Italy, findings came from initial and final assessments comparing learners who used the application with those who did not, although the report notes the sample was small at 51 students. Across these internal evaluations, the application was associated with improved language skills, stronger participation, and higher learner motivation ([↑UNICEF Innocenti, 2024](#)).

Learning focus: Language and multilingual support

Education type: Support service, curriculum addition

Technology: Mobile-based

3.1.3. All-Ukrainian School Online (Vseukrainska shkola online)

The All-Ukrainian School Online is a national digital platform developed by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine in collaboration with the Ministry of Digital Transformation and the NGO "Osvitoria." Originally launched to mitigate learning loss during the COVID-19 pandemic, it has since become the most widely used educational option for children displaced by the February 2022 invasion of Ukraine by the Russian Federation. In 2025, 1.2 million learners were reported to be using the platform for full or part time study ([↑Global Partnership for Education \(GPE\), 2025](#); [↑Osvitoria, 2026](#); [↑UN News, 2025](#)).

The platform provides a unified, government-aligned digital curriculum for grades 5–11, featuring over 2,200 video lessons, interactive tests, and comprehensive study notes across 18 core subjects. It operates as a cloud-based system that is accessible via web browsers or dedicated mobile applications (iOS and Android), with specific "zero-rated" data agreements from major telecom providers to ensure equitable access. By 2025, the platform had integrated a "Virtual Teacher's Office," allowing educators to manage remote classrooms, assign tasks, and track student progress across international borders ([↑Osvitoria, 2025](#); [↑UNICEF, 2025a](#)). No publicly available impact evidence was available as of publication.

Learning focus: Curriculum (grade 5-11)

Education type: Formal

Technology: Online learning platform supported by zero-rated data agreements

3.1.4. Amala Education

Amala Education (formerly Sky School) provides an international secondary school qualification, specifically designed for displaced youth and host communities aged 16–25 ([↑Amala, 2026](#)). It is currently available in Kenya (Kakuma) and Jordan (Amman), offering a competency-based curriculum that includes specialised modules in "Social Entrepreneurship," "Peacebuilding," and "Ethical Leadership." These courses are grounded in high-level SEL competencies, such as agency, cultural understanding, and critical inquiry. The intervention utilises a blended learning model that combines a device-agnostic online platform with intensive in-person facilitation, ensuring that learners develop both digital literacy and strong peer-support networks ([↑Amala, 2024](#); [↑UNHCR, 2024a](#)).

A 2024 internal impact report revealed that 83% of alumni credited the programme with helping them achieve their personal and professional goals, highlighting a marked improvement in resilience and the ability to navigate complex environments independently. A critical next step is to ensure that the SEL-focused diploma is formally recognised by national education systems across East Africa, facilitating easier transition into higher education or formal employment ([↑Amala, 2024](#); [↑Barnett, 2025](#)).

Learning focus: SEL and competency-based learning

Education type: Alternative secondary education

Technology: Blended learning (online platform, in-person facilitation)

3.1.5. Azima

Azima is Jusoor's WhatsApp-based distance learning intervention in Lebanon, developed within its broader Refugee education programme, which has supported displaced Syrian children since 2013. It was used to sustain learning when in-person education was disrupted, including during COVID-19 school closures and again during conflict in Lebanon in 2024. Using a platform already familiar to refugee communities, Azima delivered lessons in math, English, Arabic, and life skills to help children

remain engaged in education despite crisis conditions ([↑Boujikian & Carter, 2021](#); [↑Tutunji & Nammour, 2024](#)).

Azima also highlights both the promise and limits of low-cost remote learning in refugee settings. A 2021 survey of 196 respondents found that the main barrier to participation was access to devices rather than lack of interest: 88% of households had a smartphone, but 77% had only one, and children were far less likely to study when the father was the primary owner because he typically took the phone to work. Children also identified internet access, teacher support, and printed materials as important for participation. In 2024, Jusoor reported 272 Azima students in online learning, showing that the programme remained an active part of its education response ([↑Jusoor, 2025](#)).

Learning focus: FLN and life skills

Education type: Non-formal alternative education programme

Technology: WhatsApp via mobile

3.1.6. Can't Wait to Learn (CWTL)

Can't Wait to Learn (CWTL) is a digital, game-based learning initiative developed by the War Child Alliance (previously War Child Holland) to support children's learning in crisis-affected settings. It uses custom gaming technology for mobile, computer, or tablet, available online and offline, enabling delivery in low-infrastructure environments and supporting learning in both formal and out-of-school settings. The intervention is currently active in eight countries: Chad, Jordan, Lebanon, South Sudan, Sudan, Syria, Uganda, and Ukraine. War Child reports that CWTL has already reached over 400,000 children ([↑War Child, 2026](#); [↑Yidan Prize Foundation, 2026](#)).

Since 2020, the evidence base has expanded. [↑Brown et al.'s \(2020\)](#) quasi-experimental mixed-methods evaluation found gains in numeracy and Arabic literacy among primary-age, out-of-school children in Sudan, while [↑Turner et al.'s \(2022\)](#) mixed-methods proof of concept study found numeracy gains among lower-secondary, out-of-school learners in Lebanon. By contrast, [↑De Hoop et al. \(2019\)](#) studying a school-based implementation in Jordan, found learning gains similar to those of children receiving the standard curriculum, which the authors linked to operational challenges. Evidence on socio-emotional outcomes is mixed: [↑Turner et al. \(2022\)](#) reported stronger social bonds, collaboration, and self-esteem, while [↑Brown et al. \(2020\)](#) and [↑De Hoop et al. \(2019\)](#) found no statistically

significant improvements in hope or psychological well-being. Game-based learning was also linked to higher learner motivation, though repeated minigames could lead to boredom, highlighting the importance of content variety ([↑Barnes et al., 2025](#)).

Learning focus: FLN and SEL

Education type: Formal and alternative education

Technology: Device agnostic (mobile, computer, tablet), online and offline

3.1.7. Education in Air

During the Covid-19 pandemic, schools in South Sudan were shut for over a year, leaving around 3 million children needing educational support. In this setting, radio-based learning became an important delivery channel, especially given that 89% of the population did not have access to the internet or a mobile phone. Through the Education on Air (EOA) initiative, the Ministry of General Education and Instruction, together with UNICEF, delivered interactive radio lessons aligned with the curriculum, alongside a toll-free helpline that allowed learners to contact teachers with questions. Although no formal learning outcome data have been published for EOA, the programme reached 329,063 learners, including 168,201 girls. Internally reported feedback was also positive whereby 79.1% of learners rated the lessons as “good” or “very good,” and more than half said the programme improved their knowledge of WASH, well-being, Covid-19 prevention, and motivation to continue learning ([↑UNICEF, 2023a](#)).

Learning focus: Curriculum (varied subjects)

Education type: Formal, alternative education

Technology: Radio

3.1.8. eKitabu

eKitabu is a Kenya-based organisation that provides inclusive digital educational content, including storybooks and edutainment videos, across 13 countries in sub-Saharan Africa. It aims to increase access for learners with special educational needs and disabilities and, during COVID-19, adapted its model by developing Kenyan Sign Language YouTube videos to support foundational literacy for learners with hearing impairments. This adaptation was reported by internal documentation to improve learners’

communication skills, confidence, and learning outcomes ([↑Barnes et al., 2025](#); [↑Guglielmi et al., 2021](#)).

Learning focus: Foundational literacy and inclusive learning for learners with disabilities.

Education type: Non-formal support service

Technology: Digital content and YouTube (device agnostic)

3.1.9. Feed the Monster

Feed the Monster is a mobile literacy-learning game developed to support foundational reading skills among young learners. Originally designed to improve first-language literacy outcomes for displaced Syrian children, the app is now maintained by Curious Learning and offers literacy content in multiple languages. The game introduces learners to a fantasy world in which they help friendly monsters grow by feeding them eggs earned through completing literacy-based tasks focused on letter recognition, phonics, and early reading. Designed for autonomous play on mobile devices, the app incorporates gamified learning features and was intentionally developed to support learners' psychosocial well-being through themes of positivity, nurture, comfort, and predictability ([↑Barnes & Katrin, 2025](#); [↑Koval-Saifi & Plass, 2018](#)).

Feed the Monster allows learners to practise foundational literacy skills independently through engaging game-based activities. Mixed-methods research using difference-in-difference analysis suggests the app can promote positive literacy outcomes for out-of-school children of primary school age in conflict-affected settings ([↑Burde et al., 2023](#)). Updated, and open-source programming is available on the [Feed the Monster GitHub](#).

Learning focus: Foundational literacy; early reading; phonics and letter recognition

Education type: Non-formal; supplementary learning

Technology: Offline-capable literacy app for mobile and tablets

3.1.10. Instant Network Schools (INS) (UNHCR/ Vodafone Foundation)

The Instant Network Schools (INS) Life Skills programme is a competency-based digital learning initiative co-developed by the

Vodafone Foundation, UNHCR, and Digital Awareness UK to serve refugee and host community learners. Operating within a broader digital infrastructure, the programme provides access to a specialised life skills curriculum through an integrated online and offline platform. Learners engage with a self-paced, 15-module course featuring interactive video content, formative quizzes, and practical challenges designed to build twelve core socio-emotional competencies, including resilience, empathy, and critical thinking. The intervention is structured to allow for autonomous learning on mobile devices or tablets, ensuring that both learners and teachers can navigate the material independently in environments where formal instruction may be disrupted ([↑Setty, 2026](#); [↑UNHCR, 2024b](#)). No publicly available impact evidence was available as of publication.

Learning focus: Life Skills

Education type: Formal and non-formal

Technology: Integrated online offline platform

3.1.11. Kolibri

Kolibri is an open-source, hardware-agnostic ecosystem of digital tools developed or curated by Learning Equality and centred on an offline learning platform designed to support quality teaching and learning without reliable internet access. It is now used in 220+ countries and territories, and its library includes materials in over 173 languages. Kolibri Studio allows curriculum and content specialists to align open educational resources to curriculum standards, upload local materials, and create assessments for offline use. Recent Learning Equality updates also emphasise AI-supported content discovery and curriculum alignment to help users identify relevant materials more efficiently. Once content has been downloaded, it can be shared offline through local networks or external storage devices, making the platform especially suitable for low-connectivity and crisis-affected settings ([↑Learning Equality, 2026](#); [↑UNDP, no date](#)).

Kolibri FLY is a collaboration involving Learning Equality, UNHCR, and Vodafone Foundation, with support from Google.org, to expand flexible blended learning for refugee and host-community learners. Since 2018, the programme has operated across Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, Jordan, Mozambique, and South Sudan. The 2022 programme assessment of Kolibri FLY, drawing on a qualitative study of semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, found that the platform was widely valued for

its offline-first design, its suitability for low-resource environments, and its ability to support self-paced learning, learner engagement, and curriculum-aligned access to content ([↑Open Development And Education, 2022](#)). The assessment also found that successful implementation depended not just on the platform itself, but on strong partnerships, curriculum alignment, refresher training through Training of Trainers models, and continued attention to hardware, connectivity, and maintenance constraints.

Learning focus: Varied (includes wide-range of curriculum content and subjects)

Education type: Support service (curriculum)

Technology: Device agnostic (i.e. mobile, laptop and tablet)

3.1.12. Learning Passport / Madristi (UNICEF & Microsoft)

The Learning Passport (LP) is a digital education platform developed through a partnership between UNICEF and Microsoft with the aim of providing curricula-aligned education and life skills content and teacher training materials supporting educational continuity for displaced and crisis-affected children. The platform works off a hybrid model where learners can access content via a mobile app or through a local “hub” device that creates an offline Wi-Fi network in areas with limited connectivity. LP also aims to provide a personalised and portable record of an individual student’s progress supporting transition through the levels of education across borders ([↑UNICEF, 2025b](#); [↑UNICEF, 2025c](#)).

LP has been deployed in varied settings globally, including in crisis-affected settings such as Northern Nigeria, Ukraine and Lebanon. A 2026 UNICEF Innocenti impact study in Mexico, where the platform is locally named *Pasaporte al Aprendizaje* ([↑UNICEF, no date](#)) provided causal evidence of its educational value, reaching over 300,000 learners and teachers nationwide. The study found that learners in classrooms using the platform showed 9% higher learning outcomes in mathematics, with students who actively used the platform at school or home performing 17% better than non-users ([↑UNICEF, 2026](#)). Qualitative evidence from another [↑UNICEF Innocenti \(2026\)](#) study in Lebanon suggests the platform has been effectively integrated in teaching and learning processes with 99% of educators reporting they could successfully navigate and use the resources in their daily instruction.

Of the 48 countries where LP is implemented, however, only the 2 discussed above have published publicly available impact evidence. Moreover, implementation reporting from Honduras and Mexico raise concerns about infrastructure gaps and limited teacher engagement ([↑UNICEF, 2025d](#)), while no cost effectiveness data is available for Learning Passport in its entirety. Given the scale of implementation, it is difficult to assess the impact of Learning Passport holistically.

Learning focus: Varied (FLN, multilingual curricula-aligned education, SEL, and job-relevant life skills).

Education type: Support service (curriculum)

Technology: Online learning platform; remote or blended learning

3.1.13. Making Waves

Making Waves is a gender-inclusive interactive radio instruction (IRI) programme implemented by War Child Canada in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, building on a four-year IRI pilot in the country. Making Waves has reached more than 2,000 out-of-school children aged 12 to 16. The programme combines radio lessons with teacher-facilitated instruction and group work, integrating broadcast content into a more structured learning model ([↑Barnes et al., 2025](#); [↑UNESCO, 2023](#))

A 2021 mixed-methods evaluation by School-to-School International (STS) assessed the programme's effectiveness by comparing 10 Making Waves learning centres with 10 traditional accelerated learning centres across Kinshasa and South Kivu. Using learning assessments, psychosocial measures, surveys, and key informant interviews, the study found that students in Making Waves scored higher across all reading and mathematics subtasks than students in traditional ALPs. Qualitative findings suggested that these gains were linked to the programme's blended model, which combined clear radio lessons with teacher-facilitated instruction and group work, helping students concentrate better and reinforcing learning through multiple modes of support ([↑School-to-School International \(STS\), 2021](#)).

Learning focus: FLN

Education type: Alternative education programme

Technology: Radio

3.1.14. M-Shule

M-Shule is a student facing adaptive learning platform that utilises SMS-based artificial intelligence to deliver personalised, curriculum-aligned lessons to primary school learners. Specifically designed for Sub-Saharan African contexts, the intervention targets marginalised and crisis-affected households where traditional internet access is limited but basic mobile phone penetration is high. Because it operates entirely via SMS and Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) protocols, the service is accessible on any feature phone without requiring data or a smartphone, making it a highly effective tool in crisis-affected settings and remote rural areas ([↑Jordan et al., 2025](#); [↑Kotlarska, 2026](#)).

Programme reporting suggests that in remedial learning programmes across East Africa, participating learners scored 7–20% higher on exams than peers ([↑Kotlarska, 2026](#)). More rigorous evidence comes from a Kenya study of M-Shule’s SMS-based Tusome literacy booster, which used server-log analysis (n=829) alongside an experimental comparison of treatment (n=94) and control (n=85) groups, with telephone-administered ASER (Annual Status of Education Report) reading assessments and ordinal logistic regression. The study found that learners in the treatment group were 2.68 times more likely to outperform the control group at endline, indicating a positive effect on literacy outcomes. This effect is plausibly linked to the platform’s adaptive design, which provides immediate feedback and adjusts difficulty based on learner performance. Because M-Shule now operates with tiered paid plans, continued access for the most vulnerable learners may still require subsidy through NGO or donor partnerships ([↑Jordan et al., 2025](#)).

Learning focus: FLN and adaptive learning

Education type: Support service (remedial)

Technology: Mobile-based; low-tech artificial intelligence

3.1.15. ProFuturo, Rwanda Refugee Programme

ProFuturo’s Rwanda Refugee Programme is implemented with UNHCR, World Vision, the Ministry of Education, and the Salesians of Don Bosco. It equips refugee-hosting schools with an offline digital learning model that combines devices, digital platforms, and preloaded educational resources for classroom use in low-connectivity settings. ProFuturo’s broader model draws on open-code platforms, structured didactic units, and teacher

training resources, and the organisation indicates that these materials are intended to support core primary learning and be aligned with national curricula. The programme is designed to reinforce curriculum-linked teaching and learning within the formal school setting ([↑Karinganire, 2025](#); [↑ProFuturo, 2025](#)).

A 2025 evaluation conducted by Education Development Consult, found that students in ProFuturo schools outperformed comparison-school students in Mathematics, English, and Science and Technology across Grades 4 and 5, with higher proportions of students reaching nationally equivalent learning levels in each subject. School leaders and teachers also reported positive classroom effects: 93% of school leaders said digital tools increased student participation, and about 85% of teachers said the training improved their confidence in using digital content ([↑ProFuturo, 2025](#)).

Learning focus: FLN and primary-level curriculum-aligned content

Education type: Formal

Technology: Hardware, open code offline platform

3.1.16. Re:Coded

Re:Coded prepares conflict-affected youth to enter the digital economy as software developers and tech leaders in their communities. Re:Coded has evolved into a regional actor across Lebanon, Iraq, and Jordan moving beyond simple coding workshops to digital career transitions for displaced and underserved youth. Through partnerships with UK-Ukraine Tech Bridge and TalentLift, Re:Coded now supports youth to secure remote roles in UI/UX design, full-stack development, and data science. The programme uses a blended learning model that combines intensive technical bootcamps with soft skills training and mentorship from industry leaders ([↑Re:Coded, 2026](#)).

Internally published 2025 success stories highlight alumni who have successfully pivoted from traditional degrees such as engineering or pharmacy to launching ethical design studios and tech start-ups. The programme's impact reporting indicates that focusing on high-growth industries provide the best opportunities for displaced youth to achieve income parity with their peers. However, the programme requires baseline digital literacy and stable internet access which may exclude the most marginalised learners ([↑Re:Coded, 2024](#); [↑Re:Coded, 2025](#)). External research

on the intervention's impact, and a better understanding of the users it reaches, is required.

Learning focus: Digital skills, coding, employability, and digital career transitions

Education type: Alternative education; non-formal technical training

Technology: Blended learning; online technical bootcamps via devices

3.1.17. Ubongo Kids

Ubongo Kids delivers FLN and SEL to millions of families across Sub-Saharan Africa through curriculum-aligned edutainment broadcast on national TV and radio, using storytelling, songs, and animated characters to reach children in low-resource settings. [↑Wahome \(2024\)](#) describes rigorous external evaluations of Ubongo programming and highlights a 2020 study in Rwanda in which children watched *Akili and Me* daily for one month, alongside a 2019 language-adaptation study examining whether learning gains were maintained when content was localised for Kinyarwanda-speaking learners. Across these studies, children engaging with Ubongo content showed a 13% improvement in early cognitive skills, a 7% increase in social-emotional learning, and a 19% increase in health knowledge, with additional reported gains in numeracy and school readiness ([↑Wahome, 2024](#)).

Through a partnership with the International Rescue Committee (IRC) and the Hempel Foundation, the program has been specifically adapted to meet the needs of displaced populations in Kenya's Kakuma and Dadaab camps, as well as marginalised communities in Tanzania. By focusing on human-centred design methods, Ubongo seeks to ensure its characters and narratives reflect the lived experiences of its audience, supporting inclusion, representation and psychological safety for children in crisis-affected settings ([↑IRC, 2025](#); [↑Ubongo, 2025a](#)).

While one of its greatest strengths lies in its offline broadcast reach, the Ubongo Playroom app has also been developed for deeper, interactive engagement. In 2026, Ubongo Kids will introduce a new climate series, specifically designed to help children in crisis-affected areas process and adapt to environmental disasters ([↑HundrED Foundation, 2019](#); [↑Ubongo, 2025b](#)).

Learning focus: FLN, Science, Technology, Engineering, Maths (STEM), SEL

Education type: Non-Formal, curriculum-aligned

Technology: Multi-modal (Broadcast, Mobile-based, App)

3.2. Teacher professional development

This subsection examines interventions that strengthen teachers' pedagogical practice, digital capability, and capacity to support learning in crisis-affected settings.

3.2.1. Accelerating Equitable Access to School, Reading, Student Retention and Accountability (ACCELERE!)¹

The Accelerating Equitable Access to School, Reading, Student Retention and Accountability (ACCELERE!) aimed to improve educational outcomes for over one million children in the DRC ([↑FHI 360, no date](#)). The project incorporated multiple components with a focus on learning material distribution and pedagogical coaching, leveraging tablets to enable inspectors to conduct real-time classroom observation and provide immediate feedback to teachers.

In its later phases (2019–2023), the project transitioned from a focus on material distribution to tech-enabled system governance ([↑A!2, no date](#)). Specifically, ACCELERE! leveraged digital monitoring tools to enable school directors and community members to report on school status and the delivery of textbooks. The project helped the Ministry of Education identify and remove over 50% of non-existent or "fake" teachers from the payroll in target provinces between 2017 and 2019 ([↑UKaid & Girls' Education Challenge, 2022](#)). This "data-first" approach ensured that resources were redirected to actual classrooms. Following the primary phase of the project, its digital architecture was integrated into the DRC's national Education Management Information System (EMIS) ([↑A!2, no date](#)).

Learning focus: FLN and Multi-lingual

Education type: Formal Primary, System-level governance

¹ ACCELERE! was included in the 2020 version as an example of tech-enabled teacher professional development in crisis-affected settings. More recently, the UKAID and USAID-funded project adopted system-facing digital tools to strengthen school governance and management. The current status of these interventions are not known due to the withdrawal of education funding by USAID in early 2025 and subsequent closure of Cambridge Education.

Technology: Devices (coaching), RapidPro² (monitoring), Online databases (system-level capacity)

3.2.2. African Higher Education in Emergencies Network (AHEEN)

African Higher Education in Emergencies Network (AHEEN) is a network of African universities that offers diplomas, degrees, and related programmes for refugees and internally displaced persons in Africa. Its Diploma in Teacher Education in Emergencies, launched through the University of Nairobi's Faculty of Education, is designed for untrained practising teachers, teachers seeking to work in conflict-affected settings, and others interested in Education in Emergencies. The programme is contextualised for refugee, displaced, and host communities and is delivered fully online through Google Classrooms, with occasional web-based sessions. It aims to build both theoretical and practical skills for teaching in complex emergencies and across diverse sociocultural contexts .

AHEEN focuses directly on emergency education practice, including the INEE Minimum Standards, inclusion, low-resource teaching methods, school and community management in emergencies, and the role and wellbeing of teachers in emergency contexts, including SEL. The wider AHEEN approach also integrates cross-cutting electives around 21st-century skills and social-emotional learning, with active, blended, and collaborative pedagogy (↑[AHEEN, 2024](#); ↑[Burns, 2023](#)). No publicly available evidence of impact was available as of publication.

Learning focus: Teacher education in emergencies

Education type: Online diploma-level teacher PD

Technology: Google Classrooms and web sessions (device agnostic)

3.2.3. Mobile mentoring (Teachers College, Columbia)

The Teachers for Teachers initiative is a multi-layered professional development model designed by faculty and students from Teachers

² UNICEF RapidPro is an open-source messaging and data platform that lets governments and partners send real-time messages, surveys, alerts, and service information through channels like SMS, voice, WhatsApp, and social media. UNICEF describes it as a tool for collecting real-time information and supporting programmes in areas such as health, education, WASH, and child protection, including in remote settings. (↑[UNICEF Office of Innovation, no date a](#))

College, Columbia University, with strategic partnership from Safaricom and the Safaricom Foundation.

Primarily implemented to support both refugee and national educators within Kenya's Kakuma refugee camp, the intervention utilises a blended learning framework that connects in-person pedagogical workshops with ongoing peer coaching and mobile-based mentoring via WhatsApp. This digital component allows teachers to engage in "Teacher Learning Circles" where they can exchange multimedia resources, collaborate with international mentors, and brainstorm real-time responses to complex classroom issues like extreme overcrowding and diverse linguistic needs. The curriculum is specifically structured to address the unique psychosocial and professional demands of crisis-affected settings, focusing on teacher well-being alongside foundational instructional strategies ([↑Mendenhall, 2018](#); [↑Mendenhall, 2019](#)).

Evaluation data from the intervention's early phases indicates that the mobile mentoring component successfully raised teacher morale and professional self-efficacy, with a significant portion of the cohort reporting the successful application of new classroom management techniques. However, the initiative faced persistent logistical barriers, such as unreliable 3G network access, cost of mobile data, and the necessity for off-grid power solutions to maintain device usage. Qualitative feedback demonstrates a positive shift in teaching practices, but further research is required to quantify the long-term impact on student achievement and to refine how mobile platforms can most effectively complement face-to-face training in the long term ([↑Mendenhall, 2018](#)). No publicly available programme updates were available as of publication.

Learning focus: Pedagogy, curriculum support, child protection

Education type: Teacher Professional development (formal and non-formal settings)

Technology: Blended learning (in-person workshops, mobile-based mentoring)

3.2.4. Stepping Stone

Stepping Stone is Education Development Center's (EDC) open-source mobile app authoring system, designed so governments and local organisations can create locally tailored interactive learning apps without coding. It supports multimedia content and is intended for use in low-resource settings where offline mobile learning can expand access

beyond the physical classroom. In Zambia, it was used to deliver training to 77,000 teachers across 2,000 community schools. Use of a Stepping Stone teacher training app by volunteer teachers resulted in students' reading scores doubling across three language groups. EDC also reports that a randomised control trial found a Stepping Stone early-grade reading app to be more cost effective than worksheets ([↑Burns, 2023](#); [↑Richmond, no date](#)). However, no publicly available usage in crisis-affected contexts was specifically documented as of publication.

Learning focus: Teacher training and early-grade reading

Education type: Non-formal teacher support

Technology: Mobile

3.2.5. Tusome - Let's Read

The Tusome intervention is a national literacy programme implemented by the Ministry of Education in Kenya, in partnership with RTI International and previous support from USAID. With support from UNICEF, Tusome was specifically adapted to reach and include refugee learners and host communities in Kakuma refugee camp, Kalobeyei Settlement, and the broader Turkana County. It provided a comprehensive instructional package including, student reading materials and teacher guides at a ratio of 1 to 1. The intervention also includes a system-facing EdTech component, where teachers and curriculum support officers utilise tablets to conduct real-time classroom observations and learner assessments ([↑RTI, 2017](#)).

This data is fed into a centralised dashboard, allowing local and national authorities to track Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) outcomes and plan for targeted support to teachers ([↑Piper et al., 2018](#); [↑USAID, 2019](#)). World Bank evaluations further indicate that replacing paper-based reporting with tablet-based GPS-enabled monitoring fundamentally strengthened accountability, enabling CSOs to maintain a high frequency of school visits and provide targeted, data-driven pedagogical support ([↑Wilichowski et al., 2020](#)). While Tusome is celebrated for achieving learning gains of up to 1.0 standard deviations ([↑Akmal, 2022](#)), its current status in refugee-specific settings is unconfirmed. With the ongoing shift towards refugee inclusion in national systems, as outlined in the Shirika Plan, there is potential for this model to be re-extended to refugee learners supporting their learning outcomes ([↑Republic of Kenya Ministry of Interior and National Administration, 2023](#)).

Learning focus: Foundational Literacy

Education type: Formal (pre-primary/ primary)

Technology: Tablets, centralised dashboard

3.3. System and policy

This subsection explores interventions that support education planning, coordination, governance, and policy implementation in crisis-affected settings.

3.3.1. AI for education policy course & resources

FabAI provides a specialised, three-part training course and accompanying video series titled "AI for Education for Policy-Makers." Developed specifically for education ministries in LMICs, the resource demystifies core AI concepts and offers a pragmatic framework for decision-makers. It moves beyond high-level theory to address specific "system-level" questions, such as how AI can be used for teacher support, data analytics, and inclusive pedagogical design without exacerbating the digital divide ([↑FabAI, 2024](#)). As of publication, no publicly available resources are available on implementation impact or usage in crisis-affected contexts. The *AI for Education for Policy-Makers* course is currently being used to train MOE staff in Aden and Sana'a on ethical AI use for data analysis and personalised teacher support ([↑Ministry of Education, Yemen, 2025](#)).

Learning focus: Ethical AI use, data analytics

Education type: System-level professional development

Technology: Online, open-source (video series)

3.3.2. OpenEMIS Refugees

OpenEMIS Refugees is a specialised, system-facing digital management platform developed by UNESCO to facilitate the integration of refugee data into national education systems. Currently utilised in Jordan, while also being adapted for several Sub-Saharan African contexts, the platform enables the granular tracking of refugee students' attendance, academic achievement, and protection status. The system is designed to replace fragmented, paper-based records that often lead to data loss during displacement, providing a centralised, cloud-based repository that remains accessible across different administrative levels. Built on an open-source framework, the platform is device-agnostic and includes robust offline data

collection tools, ensuring functionality in environments with inconsistent internet connectivity ([↑OpenEMIS, 2018](#); [↑UNESCO, 2025](#))

In Jordan, integrating refugee data into EMIS has been reported to have streamlined refugee-status verification and reduced administrative burdens in school enrolment. [↑UNHCR & UNESCO \(2024\)](#) report this has strengthened coordination and provided more reliable data to help target support for refugee students more effectively. .

Learning focus: Data (administrative and protection)

Education type: Formal settings

Technology: Open-source framework, cloud-based repositories and offline data collection tools

3.3.3. Philippines Department of Education (DepEd) policies on climate-related distance EiE

In the Philippines, the Department of Education, working with Save the Children and the Prudence Foundation, developed a suite of digital tools to strengthen planning and decision-making across national, sub-national, and school levels. These include the Rapid Assessment of Damages Report application, which supports school-level reporting of post-disaster damage and needs so that interventions to sustain learning can be made more quickly; the School Watching Application, which supports student-led hazard mapping; and the Comprehensive School Safety Monitoring Tool, which helps schools monitor safety conditions over time and receive tailored guidance. Together, these tools support both preparedness and response by helping the education system identify risks in advance and act more quickly after climate-related disruptions, thereby reducing the likelihood and impact of interruptions to learning ([↑Brugha et al., 2025](#); [↑EiE Hub, 2023](#)).

This emphasis on preparedness is reinforced in the [↑Department of Education, Republic of the Philippines' \(2024\)](#) Order No. 022, s. 2024 , which states that when face-to-face classes are suspended, schools should shift, where feasible, to online distance learning, modular distance learning, or blended learning to maintain continuity. The policy also requires schools to develop and regularly update Learning and Service Continuity Plans (LSCPs) that identify suitable alternative delivery modes, assess learner access to devices and internet, plan for teacher mobilisation and technical assistance, and monitor the effectiveness of the modalities used. In this way, online learning is positioned not as an ad hoc response, but as a

pre-planned option within a broader climate and disaster continuity framework ([↑Department of Education, Republic of the Philippines, 2024](#)).

Learning focus: Preparedness and learning continuity during emergencies

Education type: Formal alternative education programme

Technology: Device agnostic and paper-based for offline

3.3.4. RapidPro

RapidPro is an open-source communication and data platform developed by UNICEF that supports real-time messaging, reporting, and two-way information exchange through channels such as SMS. In education-related emergency contexts, it has been used less as a direct learning platform and more as a tool for system monitoring and coordination ([↑UNICEF, 2023b](#)). For example, in Sierra Leone, UNICEF used EduTrac, powered by RapidPro, to monitor Ebola hygiene supplies in schools during the Ebola response, helping education actors track school-level conditions during crisis recovery ([↑UNICEF, 2015](#)). In Pakistan, UNICEF used RapidPro for real-time school safety monitoring in flood-affected areas, enabling school focal points to report conditions and helping authorities gather timely information to support education-system response and preparedness. Together, these cases suggest that RapidPro's main value in emergencies lies in low-bandwidth communication, rapid data collection, and school-status monitoring in disrupted contexts ([↑UNICEF, 2017](#)).

Learning focus: Data and monitoring

Education type: Formal settings

Technology: Mobile-based (does not require internet connectivity or a smart phone)

3.4. Access and enabling technologies

This subsection highlights openly available learning materials, platforms, and enabling infrastructure that support equitable access to education and/or educational content in crisis-affected settings.

3.4.1. Giga

Giga is a UNICEF–ITU initiative launched in 2019 to connect every school to the internet and every young person to information, opportunity, and choice. It maps school connectivity in real time, helps governments analyse

infrastructure and costs, and supports financing and contracting strategies that make connectivity more affordable and sustainable. ITU also helps convene governments, regulators, and telecom providers to align approaches to data costs and network access, including negotiations around zero-rating and broader connectivity policy.

Its role is to build the infrastructure, partnerships, and data systems that make internet-enabled learning possible rather than deliver instruction directly. In Kyrgyzstan, Giga's mapping helped the government save about \$200,000 per year, reduce prices by almost half, and nearly double connection speeds. In Rwanda, pooled procurement reduced the average price of internet per Mbps by up to 55%. In Sierra Leone, school and connectivity data were used to map out-of-school children and identify factors associated with learning outcomes, while Niger and Colombia used Giga-supported mapping to identify previously unmapped schools. Together, these efforts help lower data and connectivity barriers while supporting digital access and skills development, especially in lower-resource contexts ([↑UNICEF & ITU, 2026](#); [↑UNICEF Office of Innovation, no date b](#)).

Learning focus: N/A

Education type: Support service

Technology: Connectivity mapping and broadband support

3.4.2. Libraries Without Borders (LWB)

Libraries Without Borders (LWB) works to expand access to critical information, educational opportunities, and local resources for underserved communities. Its broader approach is to remove barriers to knowledge by creating sustainable solutions that bring learning materials, services, and community resources beyond traditional library spaces and into places where people live and learn. This mission underpins a set of portable and offline-ready education tools designed for crisis, displacement, and other low-resource settings.

Ideas Box is LWB's rapidly deployable multimedia learning hub: a pop-up space that can be set up in under 20 minutes and used as a school, library, or community centre, with books, tablets, computers, offline servers, connectivity, and facilitated educational and cultural activities. *Ideas Cube* is a smaller autonomous digital library that creates a local Wi-Fi hotspot so users can access offline educational, cultural, and training resources from phones, tablets, or computers. *Kajou* extends this offline-access model

further by distributing digital content through SD cards or battery-powered local servers, making educational materials available to disconnected users without requiring continuous internet access. Evidence from a 2016 RCT y in Burundi’s Bwagiriza refugee camp found that students attending French and math lessons in an Ideas Box showed 23% more academic improvement than comparable peers in standard classrooms, with stronger effects for primary learners ([↑Libraries Without Borders, 2025](#); [↑Peich, 2016](#)).

Learning focus: Access to learning and literacy.

Education type: Non-formal support service

Technology: Device agnostic

3.4.3. Zoom, Google Classroom, and YouTube

While Zoom, Google Classroom, and YouTube are not “new” EdTech tools since 2020, evidence has emerged on their use in crisis-affected settings as tools for sustaining learning, connection, and access to educational content. The literature suggests that live instruction through Zoom and Google Classroom can help maintain engagement, communication, and collaboration between teachers and learners during emergencies, with some teachers and students reporting positive experiences and confidence in the quality of learning delivered through these platforms ([↑Barnes et al., 2025](#)). At the same time, findings are mixed, as other studies point to concerns about reduced learning, teacher stress, and the added emotional burden associated with emergency remote teaching. YouTube can be used as an asynchronous learning tool that can connect learners to knowledge beyond their immediate context and support both academic progress and psychosocial well-being during crisis ([↑Barnes et al., 2025](#)).

Learning focus: Varied

Education type: Support service (curriculum and learning platforms)

Technology: Device agnostic (i.e. mobile, laptop and tablet)

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Appendix A: Summary of interventions

Name	Category	Learning Focus	Education Type	Technology
3.1.1. Ahlan Simsim	Teaching and learning	Early childhood development; psychosocial support	Non-formal education; support service	TV; digital platforms; mobile-based learning
3.1.2. Akelius Digital Learning Initiative	Teaching and learning	Language and multilingual support	Support service, curriculum addition	Mobile-based
3.1.3. All-Ukrainian School Online	Teaching and learning	Curriculum (grade 5-11)	Formal	Online learning platform supported by zero-rated data agreements
3.1.4. Amala Education	Teaching and learning	SEL and competency-based learning	Alternative secondary education	Blended learning (online platform, in-person facilitation)
3.1.5. Azima	Teaching and learning	FLN and life skills	Non-formal alternative education programme	WhatsApp via mobile

Name	Category	Learning Focus	Education Type	Technology
3.1.6. Can't Wait to Learn (CWTL)	Teaching and learning	FLN and SEL	Formal and alternative education	Device agnostic (mobile, computer, tablet), online and offline
3.1.7. Education in Air	Teaching and learning	Curriculum (varied subjects)	Formal, alternative education	Radio
3.1.8. eKitabu	Teaching and learning	Foundational literacy and inclusive learning for learners with disabilities.	Non-formal support service	Digital content and YouTube (device agnostic)
3.1.9. Feed the Monster	Teaching and learning	Foundational literacy; early reading; phonics and letter recognition	Non-formal; supplementary learning	Offline-capable literacy app for mobile and tablets
3.1.10. Instant Network Schools (INS)	Teaching and learning	Life Skills	Formal and non-formal	Integrated online offline platform

Name	Category	Learning Focus	Education Type	Technology
3.1.11. Kolibri	Teaching and learning	Varied (includes wide-range of curriculum content and subjects)	Support service (curriculum)	Device agnostic (i.e. mobile, laptop and tablet)
3.1.12. Learning Passport / Madristi	Teaching and learning	Varied (FLN, multilingual curricula-aligned education, SEL, and job-relevant life skills)	Support service (curriculum)	Online learning platform; remote or blended learning
3.1.13. Making Waves	Teaching and learning	FLN	Alternative education programme	Radio
3.1.14. M-Shule	Teaching and learning	FLN and adaptive learning	Support service (remedial)	Mobile-based; low-tech artificial intelligence
3.1.15. ProFuturo, Rwanda Refugee Programme	Teaching and learning	FLN and primary-level curriculum-aligned content	Formal	Hardware, open code offline platform

Name	Category	Learning Focus	Education Type	Technology
3.1.16. Re:Coded	Teaching and learning	Digital skills, coding, employability, and digital career transitions	Alternative education; non-formal technical training	Blended learning; online technical bootcamps via devices
3.1.17. Ubongo Kids	Teaching and learning	FLN, STEM, and SEL	Non-Formal, curriculum-aligned	Multi-modal (Broadcast, Mobile-based, App)
3.2.1. Accelerating Equitable Access to School, Reading, Student Retention and Accountability (ACCELERE!)	Teacher professional development	FLN and Multi-lingual	Formal Primary, System-level governance	Devices (coaching), RapidPro (monitoring), Online databases (system-level capacity)
3.2.2. African Higher Education in Emergencies Network (AHEEN)	Teacher professional development	Teacher education in emergencies	Online diploma-level teacher PD	Google Classrooms and web sessions (device agnostic)

Name	Category	Learning Focus	Education Type	Technology
3.2.3. Mobile mentoring (Teachers College, Columbia)	Teacher professional development	Pedagogy, curriculum support, child protection	Teacher PD (formal and non-formal settings)	Blended learning (in-person workshops, mobile-based mentoring)
3.2.4. Stepping Stone	Teacher professional development	Teacher training and early-grade reading	Non-formal teacher support	Mobile
3.2.5. Tusome - Let's Read	Teacher professional development	Foundational Literacy	Formal (pre-primary/primary)	Tablets, centralised dashboard
3.3.1. AI for education policy course & resources	System and policy	Ethical AI use, data analytics	System-level professional development	Online, open-source (video series)
3.3.2. OpenEMIS Refugees	System and policy	Data (administrative and protection)	Formal settings	Open-source framework, cloud-based repositories, offline tools

Name	Category	Learning Focus	Education Type	Technology
3.3.3. Philippines DepEd policies on climate-related EiE	System and policy	Preparedness and learning continuity during emergencies	Formal alternative education programme	Device agnostic and paper-based for offline
3.3.4. RapidPro	System and policy	Data and monitoring	Formal settings	Mobile-based (does not require internet connectivity or a smart phone)
3.4.1. Giga	Access and enabling technologies	N/A	Support service	Connectivity mapping and broadband support
3.4.2. Libraries Without Borders (LWB)	Access and enabling technologies	Access to learning and literacy.	Non-formal support service	Device agnostic
3.4.3. Zoom, Google Classroom, and YouTube	Access and enabling technologies	Varied	Support service (curriculum and learning platforms)	Device agnostic (mobile, laptop and tablet)